

Study of thermal behavior of an air-core smoothing reactor designed for the Iran's future HVDC network

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Abstract—Air-core smoothing reactors are widely used in DC transmission systems to reduce the rate of rise of the fault current, harmonics and are much favorable due to their low maintenance and operation cost beside the higher saturation points compared with the iron-core ones. The proper design of air-core reactors can play a crucial role in increasing their reliability and lifetime. One of the most important aspects of air-core reactor design which has a sever effect on its lifetime is the winding ventilation and its steady-state temperature. In this paper design of an 80mH air-core smoothing reactor is investigated through finite element method modeling of its winding temperature in its steady-state operation condition. The results show that the temperature distribution in different winding layers is highly dependent on the airflow velocity between the layers. Moreover, mounting acoustic enclosure and the rain cap at the winding top can disturb the airflow through the reactor, hence its ventilation. However, with proper design, their negative effect on winding ventilation can be decreased.

Keywords—Air-core smoothing reactor; Thermal behavior; Winding layer; HVDC systems.

I. INTRODUCTION

DC smoothing reactors play an inevitable role in the reliability and stability of HVDC systems by reducing current harmonics, transient over-currents, and other fluctuations that may occur in the system due to switching and load changes [1-3]. Two types of smoothing reactors are used in DC networks, iron-core reactor, and air-core reactor. The structure of the iron-core reactor resembles a power transformer. They have an iron-core and an oilpaper insulating system. The main structure of an air-core reactor is a hollow multi-layer winding that is typically placed on an insulating stand. Nowadays utilizing dry-type air-core smoothing reactors in DC transmission systems is on the rise due to their simple structure, easy transport, simple installation, and low operation and maintenance costs [4-6].

Given that the load current flows through the reactor (nominal DC current plus harmonics), high resistive losses occur in the reactor winding which leads to its temperature rise. Therefore, proper cooling must be considered carefully during the reactor winding design. If not, overheating or local heating in the winding can occur, which can cause permanent failure or reduce the lifetime of the winding [1, 7].

In the light of the rapid development of numerical methods and the performance of computers, many researchers have utilized finite element methods to study air-core smoothing reactors from different viewpoints [5]. For instance, [3] has used Ansys[®] software to evaluate the magnetic field distribution around an air-core smoothing reactor. In [2] and [5] the electric field distribution around the reactor as well as on its insulator surface has been assessed using three dimensional (3D) models. Given the importance of reasonable cooling in air-core reactors, many researchers have been dedicated to studying their thermal characteristics. In this regard [8] has studied the effect of the surrounding acoustic barrier around the air-core reactor winding on its steady-state temperature distribution. This research has optimized the dimensions of the acoustic barrier to reduce the sound pressure around the winding while maintaining its temperature as low as possible. In a similar approach in [1, 7, 9] the effect of the acoustic barrier and the rain cap on the winding temperature distribution of air-core smoothing reactor is investigated.

In this paper thermal behavior of an air-core smoothing reactor winding designed based on the requirements for the future network in Iran is investigated and its basic design stage is studied by analyzing temperature distribution in winding with and without rain cap and acoustic enclosure. The obtained results can be very useful in selecting proper insulation for the winding conductors and a general understanding of the thermal behavior of the designed winding.

To increase the accuracy of the analysis and obtained results, the issue is resolved in COMSOL[®] Multiphysics by involving electromagnetic fields, heat transfer in solids and fluids, laminar fluid flow, and electric current distribution all at the same time. This way, the steady-state condition of the winding is determined considering the interaction of winding temperature distribution, the magnetic field around the coil, ventilation of the winding by air, and current distribution in the winding. The interplay of the abovementioned cases is illustrated in Fig. 1.

In the following sections, first, the winding structure of an air-core smoothing reactor is reviewed, and the specifications of the modeled winding are presented. Then the governing equations of the simulations are explained and eventually the obtained results are analyzed.

Fig. 1. The interplay of different factors in the steady state temperature of the reactor winding.

II. AIR-CORE SMOOTHING REACTOR WINDING

A. Basic Structure of Air-Core Smoothing Reactor Winding

The air core smoothing reactor winding is mainly composed of several layers of coaxial coils, which are connected in parallel and each individual layer is made of one or more insulated conductors. As mentioned, layers are connected in parallel by welding their ends to the metal beam structures on the top and bottom of the winding, known as spider arms. In addition to enhancing the mechanical strength of the winding, spider arms also act as current terminals to the reactor. Also, the individual concentric layers are radially separated from each other by fiberglass sticks which form the air ducts that are necessary for the cooling of the winding [8, 10, 11]. A simplified demonstration of smoothing reactor winding is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Structure of an air-core smoothing reactor winding, (a) side view, (b) top view.

B. Modeled Air-Core Smoothing Reactor Winding

It was considered based on the available data from HVDC research center that the requirements will be a smoothing reactor at 280 kV DC (full wave DC at 400 kV AC) and about 1500 A. Generally, air-core smoothing reactors' inductance is between 75mH and 100mH [6]. With that in mind, the winding parameters were considered in a way that its inductance be in that range. It was also considered that each layer of winding is consisting of an aluminum conductor with a cross-section of 70mm². Moreover, considering that the fiber sticks and spider arms have a negligible effect on the airflow through winding layers and its ventilation, they were omitted in modeling. An scaled section of the modeled winding is shown in Fig. 3 and its parameters are listed in Table I.

Fig. 3. The modeled winding cut illustration.

TABLE I. MODELED WINDING PARAMETERS

Characteristics of the winding	Value
Reactor height	320cm
Number of layers	9
Inner layer diameter	66cm
Outer layer diameter	154cm
Space between layers	10cm
Rated DC current	1500A
Number of turns in each layer	320
Inductance	80mH

III. GOVERNING EQUATIONS

This section is devoted to explaining the physics and equations used in modeling. Three main physics, including magnetic fields, heat transfer in solids and fluids, and laminar flow have been combined and solved together. Each physics role and its basic governing equations are described herein below.

A. Magnetic Fields

The Magnetic Field interface is used to compute magnetic field and induced current distributions in and around coils, conductors, and magnets. Two major features that are used in this interface are coil and Ampère's law.

1) Coil

Each winding layer has been considered as a coil. The coil feature transforms lumped excitation into local quantities (electric field and electric current density) and computes lumped parameters of interest such as impedance, and inductance. The following equation is applied to the winding layers in the model.

$$J_e = \frac{NI_{cir}}{A} e_{coil} \quad (1)$$

Here J_e is the current density in the layer in A/m², N is each layer's turns number, A is layer cross-section in m², I_{cir} is the winding current in A and e_{coil} is the layer's voltage in V.

2) Ampère's law

This feature is applied to the winding's surrounding domain and adds Ampère's law for the magnetic field and provides an interface for defining the constitutive relation and its associated properties as well as electric properties by the following relations known as Maxwell equations and Ohm law.

$$\nabla \times H = J \quad (2)$$

$$B = \nabla \times A \quad (3)$$

$$J = \sigma E \quad (4)$$

In the above equations, H is the magnetic flux in A/m, J is the current density in A/m², B is magnetic flux density in T, A is the magnetic vector potential in Wb/m, σ is the electrical conductivity in S/m and E is the electric field in V/m.

B. Heat Transfer in Solids and Fluids

The heat transfer interface is used to model heat transfer by conduction, convection, and radiation. The solid and fluid are two main parts that are applied to different domains in modeling.

1) Solid

The winding layers are considered as solid parts and heat transfer in them is considered utilizing two following heat equations.

$$\rho C_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \rho C_p u \cdot \nabla T + \nabla \cdot q = Q \quad (5)$$

$$q = -k \nabla T \quad (6)$$

In (5), ρ is the density in kg/m³, C_p is the solid heat capacity in J/(kg.K), T is the temperature in K, u is velocity field in m/s, and Q is the heat source in W/m³ which is ascertained through resistive losses in conductors.

Equation (6) is used to describes the relationship between the heat flux vector and the temperature gradient. Where q is the local heat flux density in W/m² and k is the winding material conductivity in W/(m.K).

Surface to ambient radiation is also considered in modeling via the following equation:

$$-n \cdot q = \varepsilon \sigma (T_{amb}^4 - T^4) \quad (7)$$

Where ε is the surface emissivity, σ is the Stefan-Boltzmann constant, and T_{amb} is the ambient temperature.

2) Fluid

The heat transfer in the ambient (Air) around the winding is calculated using the following equation.

$$\rho C_p u \cdot \nabla T + \nabla \cdot q = Q + Q_p + Q_{vd} \quad (8)$$

Here u is the velocity vector in m/s, Q_p is the work done by pressure change and Q_{vd} is the viscous dissipation in the fluid both in W/m³.

C. Laminar Flow

When the air around the reactor heats up, it moves upwards, and cooling occurs through the natural airflow surrounding the winding layers. The laminar flow interface is used to compute the velocity and pressure fields for the airflow around the winding. The main governing equations are as follows:

$$\rho(u \cdot \nabla)u = \nabla \cdot [-pI + K] + F \quad (9)$$

$$\nabla \cdot (\rho u) = 0 \quad (10)$$

$$K = \mu(\nabla u + (\nabla u)^T) - \frac{2}{3} \mu(\nabla \cdot u)I \quad (11)$$

Where u is the velocity vector in m/s, P is relative pressure in Pa, F is the volume force vector in N/m³ and μ is the fluid's dynamic viscosity in Pa.s.

IV. SIMULATIONS AND RESULTS

The main objective of this study is to analyze the thermal behavior of an air-core smoothing reactor with and without an acoustic barrier and rain cap. In this regard, the winding model with and without outer accessories was implemented in COMSOL® Multiphysics. Due to the axial symmetry of the modeled structures and to reduce the required calculations for modeling, the simulations were conducted in a two dimensional (2D) axisymmetric domain. An illustration of modeled windings is given in Fig. 4 and the final revolved geometry of the windings is displayed in Fig. 5. It was assumed that the rated DC current passes through the winding and the ambient temperature is 293K then its behavior was analyzed.

Fig. 4. 2D axisymmetric modeled windings, (a) without acoustic barrier and rain cap, (b) with acoustic barrier and rain cap.

Fig. 5. Revolved model of studied windings, (a) without acoustic barrier and rain cap, (b) with acoustic barrier and rain cap.

Each winding layer's temperature from its bottom to the top is measured and displayed in Fig. 6 for both case studies i.e., with and without acoustic barrier and rain cap. The winding layers are numbered from the inward to the outward layer, respectively. Layer one is the interior layer of the winding and layer 9 is the most exterior one.

According to Fig. 6, the following can be observed:

- In both cases, the layers display a similar temperature distribution pattern, however, the winding temperature while it is surrounded by acoustic enclosure and rain cap is slightly higher.
- The inner layers in both cases are a bit warmer than the outer layers and the most inner layer has the highest temperature. Moreover, the hottest point of the reactor winding is in the innermost layer and its upper third.
- Moving upward from the bottom of the winding to its top, in the lower quarter, a significant temperature increase is observed. In the middle of the coil, the temperature difference between the parts of each layer is somewhat smaller and in the upper quarter of the layers, the temperature has started to decrease.
- There is a slight anomaly in the temperature distribution of layers in the lower quarter of winding with no acoustic enclosure and rain cap. The temperature of the 9th layer is higher than the adjacent interior layers in the lower quarter, which contradicts the expected behavior of the coil. temperature distribution in the lower quarter

of winding with no rain cap and acoustic enclosure is displayed in Fig. 7.

The current density in the winding layers and the airflow velocity around the coil layers are shown in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9, respectively. By analyzing the current density of different layers and the airflow around the windings, the observed behavior of the windings can be explained. As shown in Fig.

Fig. 6. Winding layers temperature, (a) without acoustic barrier and rain cap, (b) with acoustic barrier and rain cap.

Fig. 7. Temperature distribution of layers in the lower quarter of winding with no acoustic enclosure and rain cap.

8, the current density in the inner layers is higher. Therefore, resistive losses and as a result, their temperature rise will be more than the outer layers. The innermost layer has the highest current density magnitude (1.9A/mm^2) and the outermost layer has the lowest one (1.45A/mm^2).

Considering Fig. 9, acoustic enclosure, and rain cap act as an obstacle to the airflow. Reducing the airflow and its speed (15% reduction in maximum air velocity magnitude) leads to weaker winding ventilation, hence more temperature rise is observed for the winding with acoustic enclosure and rain cap.

Fig. 8. Current density in different layers of winding.

Also, according to Fig. 9, the cold air enters the reactor with relatively high velocity, but its velocity reduces as it moves upwards along the winding layers. The air velocity reduction and warming up due to heat absorption as it moves upwards, debilitate the air's ventilation capacity. Therefore, the severe temperature difference between the bottom and middle of the reactor layers can be justified.

Fig. 10 illustrates the airflow velocity around the winding layers in the lower quarter of winding with no acoustic enclosure and rain cap. The air velocity near the 9th layer is almost zero. This means that there is not much air ventilation there. Therefore, the lack of airflow around the coil and the lack of proper ventilation at the lower parts of the 9th coil is the reason that the 9th layer temperature at this part is higher than the adjacent interior layers.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, an 80mH air-core reactor winding with a rated current of 1.5 kA is modeled and its thermal behavior is studied. The results show that the current distribution between different winding layers and the airflow velocity between different layers of the coil play a major role in determining the steady-state temperature distribution of the reactor winding.

It is observed that, installing the acoustic enclosure and the rain cap on the winding can affect the winding ventilation and cause its temperature rise. However, with proper design, their negative effect on reactor ventilation can be reduced. In this way, the temperature rise in the reactor winding will not be noticeable.

All in all, to achieve a reliable thermal design, one must consider proper current density, proper layer distancing and suitable spacing between winding and its enclosure. Also, it is recommended that the winding layers be designed so that the airflow around them is uniform. This way, a more uniform temperature distribution can be achieved between the layers, which makes the insulation selection for winding easier and is the target of the future studies utilizing the optimization methods in COMSOL®.

Fig. 9. Air flow velocity and streamlines around winding layers, (a) without acoustic barrier and rain cap, (b) with acoustic barrier and rain cap.

Fig. 10. Air flow velocity and streamlines around winding layers in the lower quarter of winding with no acoustic enclosure and rain cap.

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REFERENCE

- [1] J. Cao, T. Chen, Z. Jiang, X. Wen, and M. Zhang, "Coupling calculation of temperature field for dry-type smoothing reactor," in *2014 17th International Conference on Electrical Machines and Systems (ICEMS)*, 2014: IEEE, pp. 3259-3263.
- [2] T. Chen, J. Cao, G. Zhou, J. Zhipeng, Y. Wang, and X. Wen, "Electric field research of ± 800 kV dry-type smoothing reactor," in *2014 17th International Conference on Electrical Machines and Systems (ICEMS)*, 2014: IEEE, pp. 1484-1487.
- [3] S. Gong, T. Li, C. Gao, J. Zhou, and Z. Chen, "Harmonic Magnetic Field Analysis based on UHVDC Smoothing Reactor," in *2019 IEEE 2nd International Conference on Automation, Electronics and Electrical Engineering (AUTEEE)*, 2019: IEEE, pp. 627-634.
- [4] R. Shulga, Y. A. Ivanova, N. Lozinova, and M. Mazurov, "Choice of line reactors for HVDC lines and back-to-back links," *Russian Electrical Engineering*, vol. 82, no. 9, pp. 469-474, 2011.
- [5] P. Wang, Y. Zhao, F. Lv, K. Li, and Y. Ding, "Distribution of electric field and structure optimization on the surface of ± 1100 kV smoothing reactor," *IET Science, Measurement & Technology*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 441-446, 2019.
- [6] M. Dong *et al.*, "Influence of smoothing reactor arrangement on transients of converter station for ± 500 kV double-circuit HVDC system," in *IEEE PES General Meeting*, 2010: IEEE, pp. 1-8.
- [7] Y. Wang *et al.*, "Theoretical and experimental evaluation of the temperature distribution in a dry type air core smoothing reactor of HVDC station," *Energies*, vol. 10, no. 5, p. 623, 2017.
- [8] F. Yuan *et al.*, "The Optimization Design of Sound Arrester for the Dry Type Air Core Smoothing Reactor Based on the Multi-Physical Field Coupling Method," *IEEJ Transactions on Electrical and Electronic Engineering*, vol. 16, no. 5, pp. 704-714, 2021.
- [9] F. T. Yuan, Z. Yuan, J. X. Liu, Y. Wang, W. X. Mo, and J. J. He, "Research on temperature field simulation of dry type air core reactor," in *2017 20th International Conference on Electrical Machines and Systems (ICEMS)*, 2017: IEEE, pp. 1-5.
- [10] D. Caverly, K. Pointner, R. Presta, P. Griebler, H. Reisinger, and O. Haslehner, "Air Core Reactors: Magnetic Clearances Electrical Connection and Grounding of their Supports," in *Minnesota power systems conference*, 2017.
- [11] T. A. Fiorentin, L. F. Lopes, O. M. Da Silva, and A. Lenzi, "Vibroacoustic models of air-core reactors," *The International Journal of Acoustics and Vibration*, vol. 21, no. 4, pp. 453-461, 2016.